

DETERMINANTS OF PROJECT DELAYS IN DIRE DAWA ADMINISTRATION: THE CASE OF GOVERNMENT OWNED CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

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Abstract

The primary objective of this research study is to investigate the various causes of construction project delays in Dire Dawa Administration. In doing so, the researcher has employed dominantly quantitative research approach and the attributes are ranked in terms of their importance by using Relative Importance Index (RII). Moreover, both descriptive and explanatory (causal research) research designs via cross-sectional survey are utilized for this study in. The data has been collected from both primary and secondary sources. Census method of inquiry is employed through distributing 102 a self-administered questionnaire to clients/government bureaus, contractors and consultants of large government owned construction projects. Relative Importance Index technique, one way ANOVA, ordinal logistic regression model and chi-square analysis are used for data analysis. The descriptive statistics result has revealed that delay in the manufacture of building materials (RII=0.81), delays in producing design (RII=0.8), low productivity level of labors (RII=0.8), insufficient work by the contractors (RII=0.78), equipment shortage (RII=0.78), material types and specification changes in the construction (RII=0.75), equipment breakdowns (RII=0.75), design engineer's inability to understand the requirements of the owner (RII=0.75), discrepancies in project designs (RII=0.74) delay in the delivery of materials on time (RII=0.74) are the top five perceived causes of large construction projects in Dire Dawa Administration. As a result, reconsideration should be due on project planning and designing of construction projects in order to find out the factors harming the possibility of timely completion of the projects in which stakeholders such as owners, consultants and contractors have clearly defined goals.

Keywords: Project Delay, Large Construction Projects, Inadequate Contractor's Work, Equipment Breakdowns, Project Completion, Dire Dawa Administration.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. A Brief Background of the study

Adequate knowledge project management practices is vital because managing projects is a complex and challenging task (Alemu, 2016). The completion of projects within the budgeted cost and timeframe is a fundamental concern for project managers.

Project management is considered an essential factor in reducing the probability of project failure, maintaining timeframes, and completing projects within budgeted costs. (JIBC, 2018).

Timely completion of construction projects is a challenging task for most stakeholders, such as governments, users, and communities. Increasing complexity in design and the involvement of many clients and contractors pose a major threat to different stakeholders for successfully completing construction projects (Doloi, H., 2009 cited in Ramlee, 2016).

According to Wang and Huang (2019), a project is considered successful if it is completed with good quality, as per the schedule within the budget. The timely completion of projects is a measure of efficiency. Over many years, various studies have been conducted to identify the factors that cause delays in construction projects. (Abdullah, 2013). Project delays and cost overruns are common in Ethiopia.

Delays in the completion of projects within the time limit have a devastating effect on all stakeholders, such as owners, contractors, and consultants, resulting in mistrust, legal battles, third-party interventions, financial problems, and a sense of misunderstanding among stakeholders. (Majld & McCaffe, 2018).

The Dire Dawa Administration (DDA) has brought about large construction projects, such as stadium expansion, Abattoir, Civic Center, and Dire Dawa specialized hospital projects. However, most government-owned construction projects in DDA did not elapse; therefore, the focus of this study is to ascertain the causes of delays in construction projects being carried out by DDA.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Abd El-Razek et al. (2009) found 32 reasons for delays in construction projects in Egypt, and the most important causes include financing by contractors, owner's delay-in-payment to the contractors, and not following the professional contractual agreement. Frank et al. (2010) investigated the causes of delays in construction projects in Ghana through Relative Indicator Index (RII) by considering them as respondents of the study.

The study revealed that all stakeholders, such as clients, consultants, and contractors, agreed that financial problems were the major factor responsible for the delay in completing construction projects in Ghana. Late payments, difficulty in obtaining loans, and price fluctuations were identified as the major financial factors, followed by a shortage of materials, scheduling, and controlling related factors.

Ogunlana et al. (2011) conducted a study to determine the factors responsible for delays in building projects in Thailand and identified inadequate industry infrastructure and other resources, problems created by clients and consultants, and lack of competence and expertise of contractors as the main reasons for such delays.

Sadi et al. (2013) studied Saudi construction projects and concluded that delay in payment by owners, late approval of design documents by owners, and changes demanded by owners during the construction stage were the major causes of project delays.

Al-Ghafly (2014) discussed the reasons for project delays in public water and sewage projects in Saudi Arabia and concluded that financial problems, changes in the design and scope of the project, delays in decision making by owners, difficulties in obtaining government permission, and a lack of proper co-ordination and communication mechanisms were the main reasons for not successfully completing the projects on time.

Frimpong et. al. (2016) conducted a survey to assess the relative importance of various factors responsible for delay and cost overruns in groundwater construction projects in Ghana. The study revealed that delays in payment from government agencies, improper contractor management, delay in material procurement, poor technical expertise, and price escalation were some of the important causes of delays in project completion. Al-

Momani (2017) found that in Jordan, the main causes of delay were related to project design, user preferences, weather, site locations, late delivery of materials, changing economic conditions, and increasing quantity.

Chan and Kumaraswamy (2017) identified and evaluated the potential causes of construction project delays in Hong Kong. They arrived at five principal factors: poor risk management and supervision, unforeseen changes in site conditions, slow decision-making, variations demanded by clients, and work changes.

Seifu (2019) conducted a study on the determinants of NGO water construction projects with special emphasis on Hararghe Catholic Secretariats. The findings revealed that project manager leadership skills, contractor competency, project team efficiency of project team, risk, and cost management are determinants of project performance.

In addition, Melat (2017) conducted a study on the critical success factors of real estate development projects in Addis Ababa and concluded that adequate planning, commitment of project managers, scope and work convention of a project, and control mechanisms have a significant impact on the successful completion of projects.

Scholars from different countries have highlighted that the cause of the delay of construction projects in one geographical area is not the antecedent in other geographical areas. Hence, studying this particular problem is essential to determine the determinants of large construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

- To assess the perceived determinants of delays in construction projects in Dire Dawa Administration.
- To evaluate the extent of delays in construction projects in Dire Dawa Administration.
- To rank the factors that influence large construction project delays in Dire Dawa Administration.

1.4 Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Organizational planning effort is significantly associated with construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

Hypothesis 2: Project manager goal commitment is significantly associated with construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant association between project team motivation, goal orientation, and construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant association between the clarity of project scope and work definition and construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

Hypothesis 5: There is a significant association between the clarity of project scope and work definition and construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

Hypothesis 6: The existence of a proper control mechanism is significantly associated with construction project delays in the Dire Dawa Administration.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A study conducted by Assaf et al. (2015) identified 56 main causes of delays in large construction projects. Al-Ghafly (2009) found 60 causes for delays in public water and sewage projects. He concluded that the delay was more severe in small projects than in medium or large projects. He came to the conclusion that the important causes of delay were financial problems, changes in project design and scope, slow decision-making process by owner for giving approval for the project, difficulties in obtaining license and permission from government agencies, and lack of co-ordination and communication gaps among different stakeholders.

Frimpong et. al. (2015) conducted a study to identify and evaluate the relative significance of various factors causing project delays and cost overruns in groundwater construction projects in Ghana. The findings of the study indicated that delays in monthly payments from agencies, poor contractor management, delays in material procurement, lack of technical expertise, and price escalation of materials were the main causes of delay and cost overruns in the construction of groundwater projects:

Al-Momani (2014) investigated the main reasons for delays in 130 public projects in Jordan and concluded that most of the causes were related to the project design, changes demanded by users, changes in weather, poor site conditions, late delivery of materials, and general economic conditions.

Chan and Kumaraswamy (2015) conducted a survey to evaluate the relative importance of 83 potential factors that cause delays in Hong Kong construction projects, and identified five principal factors: inadequate risk management and supervision, unexpected changes in site conditions, slow decision-making, client-related variations, and work-related deviations.

Ogunlana *et al.*, (2016) studied delays in building projects in Thailand and classified the problems of the construction industry into three categories: (i) shortages or inadequacies in industry infrastructure and resources, (2) problems created by clients and consultants, and (3) problems due to lack of technical expertise by contractors. Frank *et al.* (2016) identified that the major causes of delays in construction projects in Ghana were related to key project stakeholders, namely consultants, contractors, and clients.

Abd El-Razek *et al.* (2016) found 32 causes for delays in construction projects in Egypt. Their findings revealed that financial problems by contractors when the construction is in progress, delays in making payments by the owner to the contractor, and failure to follow professional contractual management contributed to the major delays in the completion of projects within the schedule and budgeted cost.

Abera L. and Fikadu T. (2016) in their study of construction projects under Oromia Industry and Urban Development Bureau identified proper cost management, time management and quality of leadership style as the important factors for reducing project delays.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

Descriptive and explanatory research designs were adopted in this study. The descriptive research design enables the researcher to describe the extent of delays, perceived causes of delays, and challenges in project scheduling among construction projects in the Dire Dawa Administration. Moreover, an explanatory research design is helpful in exploring the determinants of delays in construction projects in DDA.

3.2. Sources of Data Collection

Primary data were collected from selected clients (owners), contractors, and consultants of large construction projects using a structured questionnaire. Secondary data were collected from relevant reports of public service organizations in the Dire Dawa Administration.

3.3. Sampling Design

The target population for this research consists of clients/government bureaus, contractors, and consultants of large government-owned construction projects in the DDA. The census method was adopted for the sampling design.

Name of large construction projects	Client/owner	Contractors and subcontractors	Consultant	Total
Dire Dawa Referral Hospital	5	20	3	28
Civic Center	5	20	3	28
Stadium Expansion	5	15	3	23
Abattoir	10	10	3	23
Total	25	65	12	102

4. RESULTS AND DICUSSION

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Profile			Project name				Total	X ²	P-value
			Referral Hospital	Civic center	Stadium Expansion	Abattoir Project			
Gender	Male	Frequency	26	24	19	18	87	2.32	0.51
		Percentage	25.5%	23.5%	18.6%	17.6%	85.3%		
	Female	Frequency	2	4	4	5	15		
		Percentage	2.0%	3.9%	3.9%	4.9%	14.7%		
	Total	Frequency	28	28	23	23	102		
		Percentage	27.5%	27.5%	22.5%	22.5%	100.0%		
Type of Respondents	Owner	Frequency	5	5	5	10	25	6.59	0.36
		Percentage	4.9%	4.9%	4.9%	9.8%	24.5%		
	Consultant	Frequency	3	3	3	3	12		
		Percentage	2.9%	2.9%	2.9%	2.9%	11.8%		
	Contractor	Frequency	20	20	15	10	65		
		Percentage	19.6%	19.6%	14.7%	9.8%	63.7%		
	Total	Frequency	28	28	23	23	102		
		Percentage	27.5%	27.5%	22.5%	22.5%	100.0%		
Education Level	BA/BSc	Frequency	23	25	23	23	94	8.12	0.04
		Percentage	22.5%	24.5%	22.5%	22.5%	92.2%		
	MA/MSc	Frequency	5	3	0	0	8		
		Percentage	4.9%	2.9%	0.0%	0.0%	7.8%		
	Total	Frequency	28	28	23	23	102		
		Percentage	27.5%	27.5%	22.5%	22.5%	100.0%		

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 1 shows that majority (85.3%) of the stakeholders are male and the remaining 14.7% of the respondents are female. Moreover, as chi-square statistics ($X^2=2.32$) and the P-value ($P=0.51>0.05$) reveal there is no statistical difference between male and female stakeholders among the various large construction projects in DDA.

Table 2: Classification of Respondents Based on Age and Experience

Item	Type of Stakeholder	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-statistics	P-value
Age	Owner	37.36	4.89	0.925	0.566
	Consultant	37.41	6.03		
	Contractor	35.87	6.36		
	Overall	36.4	5.99		
Experience	Owner	11.40	3.04	1.028	0.44
	Consultant	9.50	3.89		
	Contractor	12.00	7.00		
	Overall	11.55	5.96		

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Looking at educational profile of respondents in Table 2, there is statistically significant ($X^2=8.12$ and $P=0.04<0.01$) difference among the education status of the respondents in which 92.2% of them are BA/BSc degree holders and only 7.8% hold Masters degrees. The mean age of stakeholders of these projects is 36.4 years. The standard deviation of 4.89 years, F-statistics (0.925) and p-value (0.566) indicate that there is no significant

age difference among project owners, consultants and contractors. The overall experiences of the respondents with a mean value of 11.55 years, the standard deviation of 5.96, F-statistics (1.028) and p-value (0.44) indicate that there is no significant difference among the respondents.

Table 3: Stakeholders' Perception towards Project Delays

			Level of construction projects delay			Total	Mean	Std. deviations	F-statistics	P-value
			Average	High	Very High					
Type of stakeholder	Owner	Frequency	6	11	8	25	4.4923	.70982	6.08	0.003
		Percentage	5.9%	10.8%	7.8%	24.5%				
	Consultant	Frequency	2	2	8	12	4.5000	.79772		
		Percentage	2.0%	2.0%	7.8%	11.8%				
	Contractor	Frequency	8	17	40	65	3.8800	.88129		
		Percentage	7.8%	16.7%	39.2%	63.7%				
Total		Frequency	16	30	56	102	4.3431	.80216		
		Percentage	15.7%	29.4%	54.9%	100.0%				

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 3, 54.9% of the respondents perceive that construction projects delay is very high and the remaining 29.4% and 15.7% of them have rated the project delay as high and average respectively. However, there was a significant perception difference among stakeholders towards project delay in which F-statistics and P-value ($P=0.03 < 0.01$) reveal that the mean perception of owners and consultants towards the project delay was significantly different from contractors' perception.

Table 4: Cross tabulation of Project name and Level of construction projects delay

			Level of construction projects delay			Total	X ²	P-value
			Average	High	Very High			
Project Name	Referral Hospital	Count	0	1	27	28	29.44	0.000
		% of Total	0.0%	1.0%	26.5%	27.5%		
	Civic center	Count	7	11	10	28		
		% of Total	6.9%	10.8%	9.8%	27.5%		
	Stadium Expansion	Count	6	8	9	23		
		% of Total	5.9%	7.8%	8.8%	22.5%		
	Abattoir Project	Count	8	5	10	23		
		% of Total	7.8%	4.9%	9.8%	22.5%		
Total		Count	21	25	56	102		
		% of Total	20.6%	24.5%	54.9%	100.0%		

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 4, 26.5% of the respondents have rated the delay of referral hospital as very high, 9.8 % of them perceive the delay of civic center project as very high. Similarly, 8.8% and 9.8% of the respondents perceive the delay of stadium expansion

and abattoir projects as very high respectively. Hence, there are perceptual differences ($X^2=29.44$, $P=0.00<0.01$) among the stakeholders towards the delay of construction projects in DDA.

Figure 4.1: Level of construction projects delay

Table 5: Stakeholders' Perception towards Owner Related Causes of Project Delays

Owner related Causes of delay	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Overall	Rank
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	
Delay in payments by owner	0.69	0.58	0.9	0.72	2
Delay in identification and hand over the site to the contractor by the owner	0.56	0.44	0.78	0.59	6
Changes demanded by owner during construction	0.78	0.63	0.79	0.73	1
Late approval of design documents by owner	0.7	0.6	0.76	0.69	3
Delay in the approval of shopfloor drawings and sample materials.	0.73	0.54	0.78	0.68	4
Ineffective communication and lack of coordination by owner and other stake holders	0.57	0.52	0.8	0.63	5
Owner's slow decision-making process	0.66	0.56	0.82	0.68	4
Lack of incentives for contractor to finish the projects ahead of schedule.	0.75	0.54	0.74	0.68	4
Work suspension by owner	0.63	0.6	0.84	0.69	3
Overall					0.67

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

The mean RII in Table 5 revealed that changes demanded by owners when construction is in progress (RII=0.73), delay in making payments by owners (RII=0.72), and late

revision and approval of design documents and work suspension by owners (RII=0.69) were the three owner-related factors in order of rank accountable for delays in project completion. The overall RII of owner-related factors was as 0.67 where respondents perceived that 67% of construction project delays were due to owner-related factors.

Table 6: Stakeholders' Perception towards Contractor Related Causes of Project Delay

Contractor related Causes of delay	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Over all	
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	Rank
Difficulties in getting finance by contractor	0.73	0.71	0.58	0.67	6
Repetition of same work because of errors during construction stage.	0.75	0.77	0.6	0.70	5
Conflicts among contractor consultant and owner.	0.81	0.75	0.57	0.71	4
Poor site management and supervision by contractor	0.78	0.76	0.62	0.72	3
Ineffective communication and lack of coordination by contractor with other stakeholders.	0.82	0.79	0.52	0.71	4
Lack of adequate planning and scheduling of project by contractor.	0.83	0.78	0.57	0.73	2
Outdated construction methods implemented by contractor	0.69	0.65	0.56	0.63	7
Insufficient work by contractor	0.87	0.82	0.66	0.78	1
Delay in site identification	0.71	0.69	0.49	0.63	7
Overall				0.69	

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 6, respondents rated Insufficient contractor work (RII=0.78), lack of proper planning and scheduling of project by contractor (RII= 0.73), improper site management, and lack of proper supervision by contractor (RII= 0.72) as the top three contractor-related causes of construction delays. The overall RII of contractor-related factors was rated at 0.69 where respondents perceived that 69% of construction project delays were due to contractor-related factors.

Table 7: Stakeholders' Perception towards Consultant Related Causes of Project Delay

Consultant related Causes of delay	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Over all	
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	Rank
Delay in conducting regular inspection and periodic testing by consultant.	0.61	0.52	0.85	0.66	1
Delay in the approval of major changes in the scope of project by consultant.	0.54	0.52	0.84	0.63	2
Rigidity of consultant.	0.65	0.5	0.75	0.63	2

Ineffective communication and lack of coordination between consultant and other stakeholders.	0.57	0.45	0.82	0.61	4
Late review and approval of design documents by consultant.	0.46	0.43	0.89	0.59	5
Misunderstanding between consultant and design engineer.	0.5	0.3	0.81	0.54	6
Inadequate experience of consultant.	0.51	0.48	0.87	0.62	3
Overall				0.62	

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As per Table 7, delays in conducting regular inspections and periodic testing by consultants (RII= 0.66), delay in the approval of major changes in project scope and rigidity of consultants (RII=0.63), and lack of relevant expertise of consultants (RII=0.62) were the top three consultant-related causes responsible for delays in the large construction projects of DDA. The overall RII of consultant-related factors was rated as 0.62 where respondents perceived that consultant-related factors accounted for 62% of construction project delays.

Table 8: Stakeholders' Perception towards Material and Equipment Related Causes of Project Delay

Material and Equipment related causes	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Over all	Rank
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	
Changes in material types and specifications during construction	0.7	0.8	0.75	0.75	3
Delay in material delivery	0.72	0.7	0.8	0.74	4
Damage of sorted materials when they are in urgent need.	0.74	0.69	0.65	0.69	8
Delay in the manufacture of special building materials	0.82	0.75	0.88	0.81	1
Delay in procurement of materials	0.75	0.68	0.72	0.72	6
Late selection of finishing materials because of confusion in choosing from different types available in market.	0.51	0.6	0.51	0.54	9
Breakdown of machinery	0.78	0.72	0.75	0.75	3
Equipment shortage	0.82	0.81	0.72	0.78	2
Low level of skills in equipment operators.	0.77	0.75	0.67	0.73	5
Low productivity and efficiency of equipment	0.78	0.74	0.58	0.7	7
Overall				0.72	

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 8, delays in the manufacture of special building materials (RII=0.81), changes in material requirements and specifications of materials when construction is in progress (RII=0.78), shortage of equipment, and breakdown of machinery (RII=0.75) were the top three material- and equipment-related factors causing construction project delays in DD. The overall RII of owner-related factors was 0.72, where respondents perceived that 72% of construction project delays were due to material- and equipment-related factors.

Table 9: Stakeholders' Perception towards External Related Causes of Project Delay

External Causes of delay	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Over all	Rank
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	
Effects of surface conditions such as soil, high water table, etc.	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.55	6
Delay in getting permission from municipality.	0.6	0.61	0.69	0.63	4
Raining during construction activities	0.4	0.45	0.47	0.44	7
Non-availability of utilities in site such as water, electricity, telephone, etc.	0.55	0.6	0.75	0.63	4
Role of social and cultural factors in causing project delays	0.64	0.71	0.82	0.72	1
Traffic restrictions at work site.	0.4	0.35	0.42	0.39	9
Occurrence of accident during construction.	0.45	0.48	0.4	0.44	7
Differing ground conditions at work sites	0.49	0.55	0.69	0.58	5
Changes in government policy and laws.	0.41	0.39	0.45	0.41	8
Delay from utility providers such as water, electricity management authorities.	0.59	0.6	0.86	0.68	2
Delay in conducting inspection and issuance of completion certificate by a third party.	0.6	0.57	0.84	0.67	3
Overall				0.56	

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 9 shows that the role of social and cultural factors (RII=0.72), delays from utility providers such as water and electricity management authorities (RII=0.68), and delays in conducting inspection and issuance of completion certificates by a third party (RII=0.67) were the top three external factors causing construction project delays in DDA. The overall RII of external-related factors was rated as 0.56, where respondents perceived that 56% of construction project delays were due to material- and equipment-related factors.

Table 10: Stakeholders' Perception towards Design and Labor Related Causes of Project Delay

Design and Labor related factors causing delay	Owner	Consultant	Contractor	Over all	
	RII	RII	RII	Mean RII	Rank
Discrepancies in design documentation.	0.81	0.8	0.61	0.74	3
Delays in providing design documents on time.	0.9	0.85	0.65	0.8	1
Lack of clear and adequate information in drawings	0.8	0.75	0.56	0.7	5
Complex nature of project design.	0.78	0.8	0.6	0.73	4
Inadequate collection of data and surveying before design.	0.86	0.85	0.5	0.74	3
Failure to understand fully the requirements of owners by design engineer.	0.79	0.9	0.55	0.75	2
overall				0.74	
Labor Shortage	0.73	0.7	0.75	0.71	3
Unskilled workforce	0.7	0.72	0.77	0.73	2
Low productivity among workers	0.76	0.8	0.84	0.8	1
Inter-oersonal conflicts among workers	0.68	0.65	0.61	0.65	4

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 10 illustrates that delays in providing design documents (RII=0.8), inability of design engineers to fully understand the requirements of owners (RII=0.75), and inadequate collection of data and proper surveying before design (RII=0.74) were considered as the top design-related causes of project delays. The overall RII of design-related factors was rated as 0.74 where respondents perceived that design-related factors accounted for 74% of delays in construction projects.

Table 11: Comparisons of Stakeholder's Perceptions towards Attributes of Project Management

Independent Variables	Type of stakeholders	Mean	Std. Deviation	F-Statistics	P-value
Project Planning	Owners	3.0800	.86217	1.571	.213
	Consultant	2.8333	.93744		
	Contractor	2.7231	.83867		
	Overall	2.8235	.86071		
Project manager goal commitment	Owners	3.2000	.64550	8.351	.000
	Consultant	2.5000	.79772		
	Contractor	3.4923	.83147		
	Overall	3.3039	.84184		
Project team's motivation and goal orientation	Owners	3.7600	.43589	2.068	.132
	Consultant	3.5000	.79772		
	Contractor	3.8308	.48635		
	Overall	3.7745	.52477		
Clarity in the scope of project and work definition	Owners	3.8400	.68799	22.323	.000
	Consultant	4.1667	.38925		

	Contractor	2.5846	1.15775		
	Overall	3.0784	1.19144		
Project manager's capabilities and experience	Owners	2.7600	.72342	1.157	.319
	Consultant	2.4167	.79296		
	Contractor	2.6769	.58916		
	Overall	2.6167	.64996		
Use of control systems	Owners	3.0400	1.59374	3.640	.030
	Consultant	1.8333	.38925		
	Contractor	2.5692	1.24962		
	Overall	2.5980	1.31450		

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 11, the F-statistics (1.57) and P-value (0.213>0.05) reveal that there is no statistically significant perceptual difference among stakeholders towards the practice of construction project planning. The finding further indicates large construction projects lack adequate project planning practice (overall mean=2.82). However, as F-statistics (8.36) and P-value (0.00<0.05) stipulate at 1% level of significance there is statistically significant perceptual difference among stakeholders towards the goal commitment of construction project managers. Contractors' perception towards the goal commitment of project managers (m=3.5 with the std. deviation of 0.83) is relatively better than that of owners (m=3.2) and consultants (m=2.5). Regarding team motivation and goal orientation, all the stakeholders have relatively similar perception. further owners, consultants and contractors have rated the project manager's capabilities and experience (overall m=2.62) and control and monitoring system overall m=2.59) as below the standard.

Table 12: Goodness-of-Fit

	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	73.530	53	.432
Deviance	59.825	53	.242

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 12, both the Pearson chi-square test [$X^2(53) = 73.5, p = 0.432$] and the deviance test [$X^2(53) = 59.82, p = 0.242$] are non-significant. This result suggests a good model fit.

Table 13: Multicollinearity Test

Variables	Collinearity Statistics		Durbin-Watson
	Tolerance	VIF	
Project Planning	0.621	1.609	1.86
Project manager's Commitment towards goal.	0.674	1.484	
Motivation and goal orientation of project team	0.699	1.431	
Clarity in the scope of project and work definition	0.591	1.693	
Project manager's capabilities and experience	0.415	2.410	
Use of control systems	0.654	1.528	

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 13 demonstrates that all independent variables are having no multicollinearity problem since the tolerance coefficient ranges between 0.42 (42%) and 0.7(70%), while VIF ranges between 1.43 and 2.41. Tolerance values **less than 0.10 (10%)** and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values **greater than 10** indicate multicollinearity (Ringle et al., 2015). Further, Durbin-Watson (DW) =1.86 indicates that there is no autocorrelation among the variables

Table 14: Model Fitting Information

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	202.455			
Final	156.155	46.300	10	.000
Link function: Logit.				

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

The model fitting information shown in Table 14 has significant value of 0.000 which describes the model is fit for logistic regression.

Table 15: Pseudo R-Square

Cox and Snell		.724		
Nagelkerke		.814		
McFadden		.554		
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	432.349			
General	410.582	21.767	27	.870

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

As shown in Table 15, the value of Cox and Snell's (0.724) and Negelkerke's (0.814) statistics indicate an obvious good fitting ability for the model; the corresponding value of McFadden (0.554) can be considered acceptable. As a result, 81% (Negelkerke's= 0.814) of large construction projects delay is determined by those statistically significant antecedents in this study. The null hypothesis is acceptable (Norusis, 2004) when P value (Doan, 2005) presents higher score than 0.05 or 0.1(McCullagh and Nelder, 1989). In the case of ordinal model, the null hypothesis is accepted since the statistical significance is 0.870.

Table 16: Logistic Regression Parameter Estimate

		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Threshold	[Level of Project Delay = 3.00]	15.045	1.232	149.034	1	.000	12.629	17.460
	[Level of Project Delay = 4.00]	17.615	1.379	163.178	1	.000	14.913	20.318
Location	Project Planning	-.901	.587	2.359	1	.000*	-2.051	.249
	Project manager's Commitment towards goal.	-.786	.623	1.592	1	0.03**	-2.006	.435

	Motivation and goal orientation of Project Team	-0.741	.739	1.007	1	.000*	-2.190	.707
	Clarity in the scope of project and work definition	-1.941	.585	11.012	1	.000*	-3.088	-.795
	Project manager's capabilities and experience	-1.086	.332	10.713	1	.001*	-1.736	-.436
	Use of control systems	-.413	.429	.928	1	.002*	-1.253	.427

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 16 illustrates that regression of the data is computed using O-logit to determine the project delay antecedents. At 1% level of significance, organizational planning, project team's motivation and goal orientation, project manager's capabilities, clarity of the project's scope and work definition and experience and use of control systems significantly determine construction projects delay in DDA.

Table 17: Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Descriptions	Estimates	Wald-statistics	P-value	Result
1	Organizational planning effort has a significant association with construction projects delays in Dire Dawa Administration.	-0.901	2.359	.000	Supported
2	Project manager goal commitment has a significant association with construction projects delays in Dire Dawa Administration.	-.0.786	1.592	.003	Supported
3	There is a significant association between project team motivation and goal orientation and construction project delays in Dire Dawa Administration.	-0.741	1.007	.000	Supported
4	There is a significant association between Clarity of project scope and work definition and construction project delays in Dire Dawa Administration	-.1.941	11.012	.000	Supported
5	There is a significant association between Clarity of project scope and work definition and construction project delays in Dire Dawa Administration	-1.086	3.587	.001	Supported
6	Existence of proper control mechanism has a significant association with construction projects delays in Dire Dawa Administration.	-0.413	0.928	.002	Supported

(Source: Own Construction, 2023)

Table 17 reveals that project planning had significant influence (beta = -0.901; wald statistics=2.359; P<0.01) on project delay; project manager goal commitment had a

significant influence (beta = -0.786 ; wald statistics= 1.592 ; $P < 0.05$) on project delay; clarity of the project's scope had a significant influence (beta = -1.941 ; wald statistics= 11.012 ; $P < 0.01$) on project delay; Project team's motivation and goal orientation had significant influence (beta = -0.741 ; wald statistics= 1.007 ; $P < 0.01$) on project delay; Project manager's capabilities and experience had significant influence (beta = -1.086 ; wald statistics= 3.587 ; $P < 0.01$) on project delay; and control systems had a significant influence (beta = -0.413 ; wald statistics= 0.928 ; $P < 0.01$) on project delay.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made to the Dire Dawa Administration to reduce delays in construction projects:

- ✓ There should be proper planning and design of the construction projects. There can be a mechanism involving all stakeholders, such as owners, consultants, and contractors, with a clearly defined goal for the successful completion of projects within the budgeted cost and timeframe. Create a list of project deliverables to meet the defined goals and specify a time limit for performing different tasks according to the schedule.
- ✓ Project managers should understand their commitments, try to identify the activities that cause failure, and work on personal development for improvement. Project managers should understand the budget, Schedule, Performance, and overall customer satisfaction. They should also build a cohesive team by being a motivator, coach, peacemaker, and conflict-handler. Facilitating training programs for project managers and the continuous updating of current trends and improvements in the construction sector by project managers should receive due attention.
- ✓ Stakeholders should develop a detailed work breakdown structure and control system to monitor work progress continuously.
- ✓ Proper allocation of funds can be done from the planning stage of the project itself so that contractors can receive regular and timely payments. Hence, clients must work closely with appropriate government agencies and financial institutions to obtain funds and credit.
- ✓ While procuring contractors, project owners must ensure that contractors are not selected only on the lowest bid. Project owners can consider the contractor's familiarity and experience, technical competence, financial position, adequate manpower, and other resources needed to complete the projects.
- ✓ There should be an effective communication system and co-ordination mechanism among all stakeholders involved in the project.

Once the site is identified, it should be handed over to the contractors immediately, for whom the project is awarded.

- ✓ All the design drawings should clearly mention the scale and its dimensions to avoid ambivalence and confusion during the construction stage.

- ✓ Proper site inspection should be done before project design so that errors can be avoided
- ✓ Establishing a systematic procedure for proper site management and supervision is essential for facilitating project planning and scheduling.
- ✓ Contractors should have a sound financial back up.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Generally, a 59% project delay was due to poor project planning assuming other predictors remained constant; 54% project delay was due to insufficient project manager goal commitment assuming other predictors remained constant; 85.6% project delay was due to unclear project scope and poor work breakdown structure assuming other predictors remained constant; 52.3% project delay was due to lack of motivation and goal orientation by the project team assuming other predictors remained constant; 66.2% project delay was due to lack of project manager's capabilities and experience assuming other predictors remained constant; and 33.8% project delay was due to lack of control systems assuming other predictors remained constant. Conceptually, it did not include project performance metrics other than time. Therefore, it could not tell about the quality and cost performance of the project, even though these three factors are interrelated. The study only focused on large construction projects initiated by the Dire Dawa Administration, and the projects initiated by private organizations and NGOs were excluded from the scope of this research. The study also employed a cross-sectional survey, which is a single-period study, and hence, can be criticized for policy direction.

6.1. Ethics approval and consent to participate

All procedures involving human participants in this study adhered to the ethical standards of Dire Dawa University, Ethiopia, as recommended by the institutional ethics committee. These standards align with the principles outlined in the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments. Informed consent for participation was obtained verbally. Participants were comprehensively informed about the study's objectives and expressed their understanding and willingness to participate freely. They were also assured of the confidentiality of their data.

6.2. Informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were provided with a written consent form detailing the purpose of the research, procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and their rights as participants. This consent was obtained in written form as the study employed hard copy questionnaires distributed to participants to gather data. Participants were ensured that their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

6.3. Consent for publication

Both the authors give their consent for publication of this manuscript.

6.4. Data

Primary data was collected from 15 clients (owners), 65 contractors, and 12 consultants of large construction projects using a structured questionnaire. Secondary data was collected from relevant reports of public service organizations in the Dire Dawa Administration.

6.5 Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the author Mr. Aschalew Mulugeta upon reasonable request @aschalewmulugeta@gmail.com

6.6 Author contribution statement

The first author Mr. Aschalew Mulugeta was involved in the design, analysis and interpretation of data. The corresponding second author Prof. AVR Pandian was involved in the drafting of the paper, revising it for intellectual content and the final approval of the version to be published.

6.7 Disclosure of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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